

Direct connection of Uni-Traveling-Carrier Photodiodes to antennas for frequency reconfigurable Fiber-Radio transmission in the Ka band

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Abstract

A compact photonic-driven wireless emitter based on a Uni-Traveling-Carrier photodiode (UTC-PD) which directly connects to a short asymmetrical inductive dipole (SAID) antenna is presented. The design exploits the dependence of the UTC-PD output impedance with the reverse bias voltage to provide maximum power transfer via conjugate impedance matching at different operative frequencies within the Ka band (26.5 - 40 GHz) with 6 dB antenna directivity and 1 GHz 10 dB return loss channel width. Electro-optical transmission measurements confirm that the photodiode responsivity is maintained throughout the whole voltage swing used for reconfigurability.

Keywords: Photodiodes, Millimeter wave propagation, Patch antenna, Multifrequency antennas

1. Introduction

The increasing popularity of wireless applications, currently ranging across communications, imaging and spectroscopy, is pushing the boundaries of antenna design to unprecedented levels, with a clear trend towards population of the higher frequency bands, mmWave and THz [1]. Increased ohmic and propagation loss brings a number of challenges related to reduced efficiency of transmitters and receivers and the need to deploy a multitude of wireless nodes to encompass the typical coverage areas. A significant trend is multifunctional front-end designs which may reconfigure to the specifics of every application. Phased Arrayed Antennas (PAAs) composed of an ordered assembly of elemental radiators may offer the flexibility to achieve the required performances, provided key issues related to the structure and optimal feeding of the elemental radiators are satisfactorily addressed [2, 3].

Compact integration of optoelectronic devices and antennas arises as a promising strategy for the future generation of high frequency adaptive wireless front-ends given the ability to directly feed the antenna element, avoiding bulky baluns and leveraging the advantages of fiber connections. Signal processing in the photonic domain may exploit wide availability of ultrabroadband cost-effective commercial components with optimal size, weight and consumption, affording

enhanced functionalities such as optical amplification, reconfigurability, and squint-free true-time delay beam steering, and enabling escalation to large PAA counts [3].

Considerable attention has been paid lately to photonic-driven wireless emitters which directly convert detected photocurrent into radiated electromagnetic waves [4]. To date, the more prominent technologies have been based on reverse biased pn junction heterostructures, such as PIN photodiodes (PIN-PD) [5, 6, 7, 8] and Uni-Travelling-Carrier photodiodes (UTC-PD) [3, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14].

The basic scheme of PIN-PDs features a depleted intrinsic absorption layer where photogenerated hole-electron pairs are driven by the bias field towards the neighboring p-doped and n-doped regions, respectively. The performance of PIN-PDs is thus limited by the typically lower transit times of holes, and the space charge effect that screens the applied field. In order to maximize speed and output current, charge transport in UTC-PDs relies on the unidirectional flow of electrons with velocities close to the overshoot limit. This is made possible by a modified layer structure with a p-doped photon absorption region next to the p-doped layer so that only the photogenerated electrons may reach the intrinsic layer to be accelerated by the field. Additional blocking layers may be employed to maximize the unipolar character of the current flow by raising re-

Figure 1: Compact optically-fed antenna design proposed, with flip-chip integration of the planar SAID antenna and UTC-PD. (a) 3D schematic, with a red arrow for the fiber-coupled input modulated optical signal and blue arrow for the biasing voltage feeding, (b) zoom-out of UTC-SAID antenna area, (c) zoom-out of flipped UTC-PD chip showing the coplanar contacts.

spectively the conduction and valence band voltage barriers before the p-type and n-type ends of the junction [4, 15, 16, 17, 18].

Further advances at the epitaxial level may be derived from exploiting waveguide designs and travelling wave structures, and from monolithic integration with other photonic devices, with special interest in optical amplification stages to boost responsivity values [19]. As compared to PINs, the superior power handling and linearity of UTC-PDs makes them ideal to exploit optical preamplification.

Optimal and direct coupling of PDs to antennas allows to take full advantage of their response response without limitations imposed by electronic stages. A variety of antenna structures has been studied for maximum power transfer via conjugate matching of the PD output impedance, with preference for planar geometries due to prospects for miniaturization, packaging and system integration [1]. Both broadband antenna designs such as sinuous, spiral, logoperiodic, Leaky wave, Bow-tie and Vivaldi, and also resonant structures based on slots, patches, dipoles and combinations thereof have been reported, with prototypes at varying frequency margins: below 20 GHz [5, 7, 20], mmWave (20 GHz – 120 GHz), [11, 21, 22, 23, 24] and THz (higher than 120 GHz), [25, 26]. Despite the extensive literature, further exploitation of tunable photodetector biasing properties for optimal antenna coupling has been found missing.

Resulting from the dynamics of the charge transport, the PD output impedance is seen to depend on the reverse biasing applied [5, 28]. On the other hand, previous works have showed the potential for passive photonically-driven emitters with a zero-biased photo-

diode [27]. Here we propose to exploit the reverse voltage as a parameter for the frequency band reconfigurability of the wireless system.

We present the design of a frequency-agile, photodiode-coupled antenna which allows voltage-controlled tuning of the radiation frequency in a broad range that covers the Ka band from 29 up to 34 GHz. The proposed coupled antenna, whose 3D schematic is shown in Figure 1, follows an innovative short Asymmetrical Inductive Dipole (SAID) geometry based on a folded asymmetrical dipole with asymmetric arms. This structure has been shown to enable direct and independent mapping of real and imaginary parts of the impedance to specific geometrical parameters with values in the appropriate ranges to conjugately match the measured UTC-PD impedances [29]. In this work we exploit this property of the SAID antenna to yield an optimal design for reconfigurability when the PD impedance is tuned by changing the reverse bias voltage. The designs presented here include slight modifications with respect to the antenna in [29] to enhance the frequency reconfigurability when directly connected to the UTC-PD.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section II the requirements for the antenna and PD impedance matching are reviewed, and sections III and IV are devoted to the analysis, measurement, simulations and design of the UTC-PD and the antennas, respectively. Finally, the more relevant conclusions stemming from the research are summarized in section V.

2. Impedance Matching

Figure 2 shows a circuit representation of the wireless front-end. The photodiode can be represented by its Thevenin equivalent composed by a source with available power P_{avs} and internal impedance Z_{PD} , while the antenna is modelled by its radiation impedance Z_{ANT} . The normalized reflection coefficients ($\Gamma = \Gamma_{ANT}; \Gamma_{PD}$) are defined as a function of the corresponding impedances ($Z = Z_{ANT}; Z_{PD}$) as:

$$\Gamma = \frac{Z - Z_0}{Z + Z_0} \quad (1)$$

with Z_0 a reference impedance given by the application and usually set to $Z_0 = 50\Omega$.

The power radiated by the antenna may be found from the power dissipated in the load of the circuit scheme in Figure 2 as [30]:

$$P_L = P_{avs} \frac{(1 - |\Gamma_{PD}|^2)}{|1 - \Gamma_{PD}\Gamma_{ANT}|^2} (1 - |\Gamma_{ANT}|^2) \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: Equivalent Thevenin circuit of the Photodiode and Antenna system.

The radiated power is maximum, i. e. $P_L = P_{avs}$, when the impedance of the antenna and photodiode are complex conjugates $Z_{ANT} = Z_{PD}^*$. From (2), the return loss may be found as [30]:

$$R_L = 10 \log \left(1 - \frac{(1 - |\Gamma_{PD}|^2)(1 - |\Gamma_{ANT}|^2)}{|1 - \Gamma_{PD}\Gamma_{ANT}|^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

3. Photodetector Characterization

The integrated model proposed is a research prototype from *III-V* Labs and it consists on an UTC-PDs based on Metalorganic Vapor Phase Epitaxy (MOVPE) growth. The photodiode incorporates a multimode planar input waveguide, an etched facet with a lens to increase the fiber alignment tolerance and photodiode mesa defined using a mix of Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) dry and wet etching. The responsivity with a lensed fiber (4 – 5 μm fiber mode diameter) is 0.7 A/W at an optical wavelength $\lambda = 1550 \text{ nm}$ with a very low polarization dependent loss below 0.5 dB [31, 32]. A picture of the actual prototype in the probe station under fiber illumination can be found in [29].

Both impedance and electro-optical end-to-end transmission data corresponding to this side-illuminated UTC-PD have been recorded through G-S-G coplanar probe station contacts with 150 μm pitch.

In a first round of experiments, the scattering parameters of the UTC-PD were measured with the aid of a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA). The details of the experimental arrangement and connections can be schematically seen in Figure 3. The UTC-PD was reverse biased with voltage values ranging from 0.5 V to 2.5 V. A resistor served as PD current control monitored through an ammeter arranged in series.

Previous to the impedance measures, an Open-Short-Load (OSL) on-wafer calibration was carried out at the tips of the wafer probe connected to port 1 of the VNA (labelled GSG wafer in Figure 3). Once calibrated, the

probe station tips were applied to the UTC-PD coplanar line contacts.

The results from the calibrated impedance measurements of the unilluminated UTC-PD in the 20 – 40 GHz spectral margin for voltage bias values ranging from 0.5 V to 2.5 V are shown in Figure 4. While the resistive part of the UTC-PD remains almost unaltered and flat with values within the margin $11 \Omega < R_{UTC} < 30 \Omega$, significant changes of the reactance can be observed, showing a positive slope against frequency and different curve levels depending on the biasing voltage. Taking as a reference the central 30 GHz frequency, the imaginary impedance goes from a value of -36.46Ω at 0.5 V to around twice this value, -81.46Ω at 2.5 V, while at 35 GHz it goes from a value of -30.03Ω at 0.5 V to -68.45Ω at 2.5 V.

In view of the potential exploitation of this findings to the design of a tunable multifrequency photonically driven antenna, we explored the effect of the biasing voltage change on the UTC-PD responsivity through EO transmission measures.

For electro-optical transmission measurements, a round of experiments considering the laser heterodyning set-up shown in Figure 3 is performed. In this scheme, the RF signal frequency is determined by the spectral distance in between the wavelength of two lasers, a Distributed Feedback Bragg (DFB) laser at the wavelength $\lambda = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$ and an external cavity laser (ECL) which allows for accurate wavelength selection with 10 pm steps in between 1520 nm and 1570 nm. The outputs of both lasers are connected to an optical coupler to provide the UTC input. An optical polarization controller in one of the coupler inputs is adjusted to align the polarization of the optical signals coming from each laser and maximize the detected power. The measured output optical power level of the DFB is around 6 dBm while the tunable laser gives around 4 dBm,

Figure 3: Experimental setup for extended frequency EO transmission measures with laser heterodyning.

Figure 4: UTC-PD measured impedance parts for different biasing voltages (colored) and simulated conjugate impedance of TA and RA designs (greyscale), (a) real part (b) imaginary part.

yielding a coupler output power around 5 dBm. An external bias-tee with maximum working frequency of 50 GHz was employed for the UTC biasing. The fiber is aligned with the UTC-PD sensitive area achieving a photocurrent reading of 200 μm . Higher photocurrent levels may be achieved by improving the light coupling into the photodiode by the use of e. g. a lensed fiber, but this is an adequate value for the purposes of this research.

The UTC output signal was read with an Electrical Spectrum Analyzer (ESA) in the frequency margin 0 – 40 GHz. To calibrate the response, and compensate

Figure 5: Measured spectral power for different photodiode reverse biasing voltages.

for the cable and bias-tee effects, the losses of the cable that connects the wafer probe with the ESA are measured by connecting the cable between a VNA, which provides the input RF signal, and the same ESA and measuring the output power in the RF frequency margin. Figure 5 shows both the direct ESA peak measure with UTC-PD and the relative measure with VNA reference compensation. This results confirm the stability of the UTC responsivity when switching the biasing voltage with transmission response values in the -35 dB range with around ± 2 dB variation margin in the 0 – 40 GHz frequency band.

4. Antenna Design

The Short Asymmetric Inductive Dipole (SAID) geometry considered for the photonically-driven wireless emitter is shown in Figure 6. The details of its operation and main characteristics have been described in [29]. In this paper we present results based on the measurements, full-wave simulation with CST Studio and EM simulations with Advanced Design Studio (ADS) of the test antenna (TA) of [29], as well as the details of the design of an antenna optimized for reconfigurability (RA), along with numerical results to assess their performance. A picture of the fabricated test antenna (TA) can be found in [29].

Figure 6: Antenna geometry and dimensions.

For the TA, a double side metallized 1.5 mm thick Rogers RO4003 substrate has been employed. The metallization coatings are made of copper with 17 μm thickness. The antenna geometry, with values of the dimensions shown in Figure 6 taken from [29], has been patterned on one of the metallic sides, while the other metallic side acts as a reflector plane at an effective length $\lambda_{eff}/4$ to achieve a unidirectional directive radiation pattern.

Figure 4 contains the simulated value of the TA conjugate impedance (grey lines) in a frequency margin

of 20 – 40 GHz. By comparing with the calibrated measured impedance values from our UTC-PD (colored lines), it can be foreseen how the TA structure may allow to maximize the power transfer from the UTC-PD by providing a complex conjugate matching in the Ka band. To confirm that, the expected return loss is computed from (3) with the measured values of the TA and UTC-PD impedance, showing the curves of Figure 7. It is seen how the return loss response may be changed by the tuning of the reverse UTC-PD bias, with very good return loss values, higher than 10 dB, for bias values in the range 0.5 V – 1.5 V with well matched operative frequencies from 24 GHz to 26 GHz, but the return loss response is seen to severely degrade for bias voltages 2 V – 2.5 V. Nevertheless these results are promising because they show evidence regarding the potential for the control of the antenna operative frequency through the reverse biasing voltage of the UTC-PD. On the other hand, the radiation pattern of the TA shows a significant disparity (see Figure 7b and 7c) due to the substrate structure used.

Figure 7: Return loss (a) and Radiation Pattern on XZ plane (b) and YZ plane (c) of TA emitter at different values of the UTC-PD biasing voltage.

The versatility of the SAID antenna design has been exploited to find an optimized antenna design, labeled Reconfigurable Antenna (RA), by tuning the antenna parameters H_2 and W_2 using ADS to fulfil respectively the conditions $15 \Omega < Z_{real} < 19 \Omega$ and $68 \Omega < Z_{imag} < 70 \Omega$ within the spectral range 25 – 35 GHz, to achieve conjugate impedance match with the photodiode, i. e. $Z_{ANT} = Z_{PD}^*$, with the remaining features unaltered. The tuned geometrical parameters of the designed antenna

are displayed in Table 1, comparing the dimensions of the designed RA with the TA. Table 2 shows the values of the dimensions which are common to both the TA and the RA.

Table 1: Test vs Reconfigurable Antennas Dimensions and Parameters

	TA	RA
$H_2(mm)$	0.522	0.505
$W_2(mm)$	0.480	0.336
$t_{rog}(\epsilon_r = 3.63)(mm)$	1.50	–
$t_{rog}(\epsilon_r = 3)(mm)$	–	0.25
$t_{roha}(\epsilon_r = 1.05)(mm)$	–	2.88

Table 2: Dimensions common to both TA and RA designs (in mm)

H_T	H_1	H_3
2.210	1.170	0.190
G_1	G_2	W_1
0.070	0.070	2.500
W_3	W_4	W_5
0.100	0.060	0.230

Figure 8 shows the return loss computed with the simulated impedance of the RA model. It is observed that when switching the bias voltage, the operative

Figure 8: Return loss (a) and Radiation Pattern on XZ plane (b) and YZ plane (c) of RA emitter at different values of the UTC-PD biasing voltage.

frequency may be continuously tuned along the Ka band achieving multiband operation by reconfiguring the UTC-PD reverse voltage. As seen, the return loss curves show excellent behavior as the center frequency is tuned, with return loss values better than 10 dB for operating frequencies from 28 GHz up to 32 GHz, by changing the reverse UTC-PD bias from 0.5 V to 2.5 V.

In addition to this geometrical optimization, a modified substrate structure consisting on a Rogers RO3003 layer placed over a Rohacell material with the dimensions specified in Table 1 is proposed in order to improve the radiation operation. The CST results shown in Figure 8b and 8c confirm very similar radiation patterns for the whole Ka band with antenna directivity values around 6 dB for RA.

Table 3: RA emitter performance values for different reverse bias voltages

Reverse Bias Voltage (V)	0.5	1	1.5	2	2.5
Central Frequency (GHz)	29.7	30.5	31.5	32.5	33.2
10dB Bandwidth (GHz)	1.60	1.62	1.43	1.25	1.02
Directivity (dB)	6.32	6.44	6.21	6.31	6.43
XZ Beam width 3dB (deg)	139.3	142.0	150.8	152.4	152.4
YZ Beam width 3dB (deg)	115.0	116.0	116.6	117.3	119.4

Table 3 provides a summary of the RA based opto-antenna performance at these resonance frequencies, obtained for different biasing voltages. The performance parameters yield similar values at the different operation bands with 10 dB bandwidth above 1 GHz and antenna directivity around 6 dB.

5. Conclusions

A compact design of a photonic-driven antenna emitter with reconfigurable RF carrier frequency within the Ka-band based on a UTC-PD directly connected to a SAID folded asymmetrical dipole antenna has been presented. Variation of the UTC-PD biasing voltage in the margin 0.5 V to 2.5 V has been shown to provide control over the wireless carrier frequency in between 29 – 34 GHz with 10 dB Return Loss bandwidths above 1 GHz and with excellent radiation pattern characteristics, unchanged over the whole reconfigurable margin and with 6 dB directivity. Electro-optical transmission measurements with a laser heterodyning

setup have confirmed that the UTC-PD responsivity is maintained for the whole biasing voltage swing used for reconfigurability. Thanks to the versatility of the SAID planar antenna design, just two geometrical parameters which respectively control the real and imaginary parts of the antenna impedance, need to be adjusted for optimized conjugate-matched PD-antenna coupling, showing promise for the SAID structure to become a basic building block of wireless devices that connect to sources and loads with arbitrary impedance. The photonic-driven SAID antenna design is compact and low-cost and thus it holds potential as a fundamental enabler of the future growth of wireless applications.

Acknowledgments

This work was partly funded by the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (MICINN) under projects PID 2019-107885GB-C31 and VERNONET (RTI2018-097051) and by the Catalan Research Group grant 2021 SGR 01415 and the University and Research Aid Management Agency (AGAUR) with pre-doctoral grant 2021 FISDU 00094 to the first author. (*Corresponding author: Sara Vega*).

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